

THE 19TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
**DELAMINATION PERFORMANCE OF TUFTED
CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES MADE BY AUTOMATED DRY
FIBRE PLACEMENT**

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1 Introduction

In contrast to their high in-plane performance, composite materials are likely to undergo cracking at ply interfaces under out-of-plane loading, leading to interlaminar delamination. The use of reinforcing elements inserted through the thickness of the composite and sometime referred to as *micro*-fasteners, such as Z-pins, stitches or tufts can increase the out-of-plane toughness and improve the delamination resistance of composites [1, 2, 3]. Through-the-thickness reinforcement (TTR) of polymer matrix composites by the process of robotic tufting has been demonstrated to increase significantly the mode I delamination resistance [4, 5, 6] as well as improve the delamination performance in mode II [5]. The ultimate in-plane strength and stiffness may be reduced due to fibre breakage and local fibre misalignment generated during the tufting process [4]. However, the extent of improvement in out-of-plane performance and degradation of in-plane properties of tufted composite structures depends on the tufting thread type and size, fabric type and lay-up and parameters such as areal tuft density, and speed. The tufting process typically uses commercial threads made from carbon, glass or aramid, with the latter being the most robust [7].

Recent studies have identified the fibre arrangement within and around the impregnated tuft as one of the critical aspects in determining the micro-mechanisms of failure and, eventually, the overall mechanical performance of the reinforced laminate [5, 8]. The particular fibre architecture in the vicinity of the tuft determines the distribution of features such as resin rich regions, fibre spreading, or variations in fibre volume fraction. The dry tufting thread conforms to the surrounding environment upon insertion and it becomes integral part of it after infusion; the final local morphology depends on its interactions with the surrounding

composite during all the subsequent stages of manufacturing.

Research studies have addressed the behaviour of tufted composite laminates made from non-crimp, woven and pseudo-unidirectional fabrics [2, 4, 5]. In contrast, no information is currently available on the delamination resistance of composite parts manufactured by automated dry fibre placement (ADFP) and reinforced by tufting. The ADFP technique uses sets of narrow slit tapes to produce the preform by means of robotic deposition. The deposition process is combined with consolidation due to the action of heat and pressure on binder pre-dispersed in the fibre tows. Consolidated ADFP preforms are not as easy to tuft as standard, unbindered materials as the limited mobility of the fibres hinders the insertion of the tufting needle [7]. This limits the grades of suitable thread to the strongest, as brittle filaments tend to break upon insertion. The interaction of the thread with the particular surroundings of an ADFP consolidated preform may also influence the overall mechanical performance of the composite produced.

This paper reports the use of a combination of techniques for the manufacture of a complex composite structure, the associated characterisation of the delamination performance and the implication of current knowledge on through-the-thickness reinforcement on the design of complex composite components.

2 Manufacturing

2.1 Procedure

Automated tufting was applied to the case of a composite tail cone, developed within the European project ADVITAC [9], comprising a conical skin of variable thickness and incorporating openings as well as ten Ω -stiffeners. The aim of tufting was to

increase the performance of the skin-to-stiffener interface to a sufficient level to replace traditional mechanical fasteners. The development of the manufacturing process was divided into three main steps: (i) determination of auxiliary materials such as tufting thread and supporting material; (ii) implementation of automated tufting on the complex shape of the tail cone; and (iii) tufting of the final structure using a tufting head (KSL KL 150) mounted on a 6-axis robot (Kawasaki FS 20N).

Preliminary tufting trials were carried out on flat panels in order to find an appropriate combination of tufting thread and supporting material. The latter is crucial as it affects the tufting loop formation and, depending on the geometry of the structure and its application, it may be left inside the structure during the entire service life, rather than being removed prior to infusion procedure [7]. The result of the tufting trials revealed that the SOMAC Kevlar[®] TKT40 thread suits the tufting process the best. The automated tufting process was preliminarily applied to a quarter of the tail cone containing only two Ω -stiffeners and the support determined by the initial tufting trials (figure 1). Figure 2 illustrates the cross-section of one of the stiffeners with the tuft layout and configuration. The dry preform was manufactured by ADFP deposition using Hexcel HiTape[®] based on HexTow[®] (table 1). Four tufting rows were inserted in each stiffener (two rows per flange at a distance of 5 mm), as shown in the inset in figure 3. The tufts had pitch of 5 mm. It should be noted that the tooling arrangement and part geometry necessitated 'blind' tufting, as there was no visual or physical access to the backside of the preform, where the foam into which the thread loops are formed was located, fully enclosed within solid channels hidden by the skin preform itself. As a consequence, the process relied solely on the use of CAD data for the accurate identification of the insertion points on the part. All tufting points and their insertion directions (approximately 13,000 for the full tail cone) were located on the CAD model, generated and exported in a format of point and vector coordinate triplets as ASCII file using CAT. Figure 4 illustrates an example of a stiffener in the CAD-file showing the tuft insertion points on two flanges and the corresponding vectors for one flange. An in-house code has been developed for tracking the spatial movement of the robot on the basis of the coordinates generated by the CAD file.

The code uses an MS Excel interface for inputting the tufting point and vector triplets. Subsequently, the coordinates are transformed into the Cartesian coordinate system of the tufting robot by a coordinate transformation and a series of commands is sent to the robot controller to move it to the insertion location. This is repeated sequentially for each tuft insertion. It should be noted that the blind nature of the operation requires frequent checking of the position of the tufting needle with respect to the flange by the operator. A command button is incorporated in the interface, for enabling the adjustment of the needle position to the correct insertion point should this become necessary during the process.

2.2 Challenges

The tufting process of such a complex geometry component involves several challenges. The shape of the tail cone involves double curvature and variable preform thickness. Consequently, the accuracy of the coordinate transformation is of paramount importance. The transformation was determined by using at least four reference points on the tool within the envelope of the robot; with the use of more than four reference points being preferable to average out discrepancies between the actual and CAD geometry. This effect was intensified by the small width of the flanges, which naturally generates a less well-posed coordinate transformation when the reference points are close to a geometrical entity of interest of an elongated shape in order to minimise the effects of errors. Furthermore, the aim was to tuft parallel to the walls of the backing material grooves rather than normal to the skin; as a result the tufting head had to rotate along two axes. This led to a further challenge: the pressure foot did not lay flat onto the preform surface as in an ideal scenario. The role of the pressure foot is to compress the preform to near-net shape while the tufting needle penetrates it and, simultaneously, hold the inserted thread in place in order to avoid pulling out the previously inserted tuft. The fulfilment of this role relies on the correct inclination of the tufting head and may be facilitated by a lower tufting speed. In the case of tufting of the stringers, failure to address this issue might have led to hitting the tool with the needle during tufting, with the potential of damaging the needle and/or the tool.

The limited envelope of the robot compared to the size of the tool posed a significant challenge. The tufting of the whole tail cone was divided into ten steps: one half of two adjacent stiffeners were tufted within each step, with a new coordinate transformation being necessary at the beginning of each step. This increased the time and effort required for the process and also increased the probability of errors in the coordinate transformation process.

The construction of the tufting head and the motor power to drive the needle shaft do not facilitate insertion through the bindered material. Repeated insertion leads to blunting of the needle tip which further hinders the process. Furthermore, local variations of the preform thickness generate further challenges as (i) thick areas are more difficult to tuft and (ii) thickness variation have to be mapped very accurately in the CAD representation of the geometry. This generates the need for manual facilitation of the insertion of the needle and frequent interruptions of the process for repositioning of the needle with respect to the preform and its normal direction. Possible enhancements of the process to overcome or limit some of these difficulties are the incorporation of information from the control of the fibre placement process in the CAD representation of the tooling/preform assembly and the heating of the preform during the tufting operation.

3 Design for manufacture in tufted composites

Reinforcement by tufting is still not fully explored in the design and manufacturing of composite structures. Many questions relevant to design optimisation arise when tufting of structures is considered and the information currently available can only partially resolve the associated issues.

The definition of a tuft density governs the balance between achieving significant improvements in delamination toughness and degrading the in-plane properties. Naturally, there is minimum amount and an upper limit of tufts to be inserted to achieve adequate and efficient reinforcement for a composite structure. This has been investigated in [5] with testing specimens with two different areal tuft densities (0.5% and 2%) in mode I and mode II. Both densities improved the interlaminar toughness

but also caused some defects such as resin rich pockets, and fibre misalignment and breakage leading to a reduction in compressive and tensile strengths. The choice of an appropriate areal tufting density also depends on the tufting thread diameter. The reasons for this are the generation of disturbances (fibre breakage and misalignment) into the dry fabric with too many tufts and resin rich pockets which might coalesce creating relatively large resin surfaces. On one hand, a thicker thread may offer higher load bearing capabilities, on the other hand the thickness is limited by the diameter of the needle eye through which the thread runs, and hence, crucial for the loop creation. Finally, tuft density, thread thickness and needle eye diameter are linked to each other and may affect the delamination performance of a structure. An efficient way to reinforce structures is localised tuft insertion with varying tuft density depending on structure loading conditions. It would be possible to tuft with thicker threads and adapt the tuft density to the thread thickness and the grade of reinforcement needed for the structures. The eye of the commercially available needles have a diameter of 0.6-1 mm. Modification of the needle design to accommodate larger threads will necessarily imply an increase of the overall diameter of the needle in order to withstand the applied loads during the tufting process which, in turn, may have an effect on the level of damage caused to the fabric.

Localised reinforcement of complex real-life structures, like the one described in the present work, usually involves tufting of preforms of variable thickness. In order to be able to tuft such preforms within the same process the needle penetration depth has to be adjusted according to the thickness of the substrate being penetrated. Commercial tufting heads mounted onto robots offer either mechanical adjustment of the penetration depth performed manually, or electronically controlled adjustments. In the latter case it is possible to program the tufting routine so that the penetration depth accommodates thickness variations. This type of implementation would guarantee a consistent tufting loop length and uniform structure thickness or fibre volume fraction.

In principle, the possibility of controlling accurately the penetration depth may be beneficial also to the implementation of 'partial' tufting, i.e. the insertion

of the thread through a portion of the preform thickness rather than through the whole of its section. In this case, the tufting loops are created inside the fabric stack and are not visible on the back surface of the preform. The advantage of such arrangement is the reduction in thickness or volume fraction variation as no resin rich layer is created around the loops. The main disadvantages of such approach involve: difficulties in controlling the tuft length and thread deposition, a potentially less effective reinforcement when compared to full thickness insertion, and the creation of a resin rich area within the tufting loops inside the preform. The consistency of the loop length is governed to a large extent by the interaction between the thread and the dry preform. The friction keeps the thread and loops in place but frictional forces may vary locally due to fibre waviness and misalignment.

Fully inserted tufts and the surface loops assist progressive failure of the structure since the increased influence of ‘snubbing’ may lead to thread ploughing into the composite prior fracture during pull-out. Delamination tests of partially tufted specimens have never been carried out and, therefore, no reliable result on the efficiency of partial tufts exists at this moment. An unusual way to achieve partial tufts with a consistent tuft length is tufting completely through the preform and trimming the surfacing loops off. Compared to conventional partial tufts, this could avoid the creation of a resin rich area within the tufting loop inside the preform and a uniform tuft length is guaranteed.

A further potential use of partial tufting is around joints. In this case, tufts can be used to reinforce the interface by tufting through a few layers adjacent to it, whilst the majority of the material remains unaffected by the operation. This can potentially achieve a good compromise between enhancing the delamination resistance and degrading the in-plane properties for the adherends. The current technology also allows insertion of inclined tufts. Cross patterns are also possible. This capability can be used in two ways in real structures subjected to complex loading. The tufts can be oriented so that they can deal better with mixed mode delamination conditions when the mode mix is known *a priori*. Furthermore, in situations where the structure is under variable loading a variety of tuft orientations can be used to

produce the equivalent of a quasi-isotropic response for the out-of-plane behaviour of a composite.

4 Delamination behaviour – preliminary tests

The influence of the thickness of the preform on the delamination response of tufted materials was investigated to evaluate the effects of thickness variation in real components. Studies on other through-the-thickness reinforcement methods, such as Z-pinning, have shown that increasing the laminate thickness increases the resistance to crack propagation [10].

Delamination specimens were manufactured with two different thicknesses, 4 mm and 8 mm, reinforced by tufting through-the-thickness using an aramid thread (table 1) and tested in mode I.

Sigmatex NCF carbon fabric of 1010 g/m² weight was used with a [0/90]_s layup. The fabric was laid-up with the 0° ply orientation parallel to the longitudinal axis of the specimens. Four layers of the fabric were needed to produce the 4 mm thick specimens. A 50 mm long and 10 µm thick PTFE film was placed in the mid-plane to act as a crack starter. Tufts were inserted following a square pattern with an areal tuft density of 0.5% and keeping the loop length within 3-4 mm in order to avoid the formation of a thick resin rich layer. The tufted preforms were impregnated with HexFlow® RTM6 by resin transfer moulding (RTM), followed by curing, demoulding and cutting of the specimens. Load-introduction steel blocks were bonded with a structural adhesive (Huntsman Araldite 420). A schematic of a tufted mode I double cantilever beam specimen is illustrated in figure 5. For mode I tests the standard procedure for unidirectional composites without Z-reinforcement (ISO 15024:2001) was followed using a Zwick electro-mechanical testing machine with a 2 kN load cell.

Figure 6 illustrates representative mode I R-curves which show an improvement by a factor of 2 and 2.5 for 8 mm and 4 mm thick specimens, respectively, compared to the control. The G_{IC} of the untufted specimen reaches a plateau at approximately 620 J/m². Tufting improves the crack propagation resistance to up to 1900 J/m² for 8 mm thick specimens and 2000 J/m² for 4 mm thick materials with an average value of 1300 J/m² and 1600 J/m²,

respectively. All curves show a typical stick-slip behaviour which was also observed in [5] and it is believed to be a consequence of the presence of the non-structural stitches in the NCF and the tufts in the reinforced specimens.

The observed effect of thickness is unexpected, since with increasing thickness the stiffness of the specimen rises restricting the bending of the beam halves. This leads to an interaction of several tuft rows which resist crack propagation. Hence, thicker specimens are expected to absorb higher energy levels and dissipate the energy at higher loads. It is also assumed that an increase in thickness enhances the frictional effects between the thread and the composite, as the extent of the interface is increased. The higher friction actually holds the thread in place and reduces the probability of thread pull-out during testing. It is possible that the micromechanics of failure of tufts have a different dependence on sample thicknesses than the previously observed dependence in Z-pinned laminates, nevertheless this requires further investigation. Single-tuft tests [8] are well suited to elucidate the effects of a single test parameter on the bridging behaviour of any *micro*-fastener and results from these and further DCB tests in mode I and mode II will be included in the presentation.

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Material	AS7 carbon fibre	Aramid
Tensile Strength	4,830 MPa	2,920 MPa
Tensile Modulus	241 GPa	71 GPa
Ultimate Elongation at Failure	1.8%	3.5%
Density	1.79 g/cm ³	1.44 g/cm ³
Weight/Length	0.800 g/m	0.092 g/m
Tow Cross-Sectional Area	0.45 mm ²	0.05 mm ²
Filament Diameter	6.9 μm	12 μm

Table 1. Material properties

Fig. 2. Schematic of an Ω-stiffener cross-section

Fig. 1. Quarter of the tail cone being tufted

Fig. 3. Tail cone made of carbon composite. The inset illustrates the detail of tufting on one of the stiffeners.

Fig. 4. Demonstration of a stiffener in the CAD-file

Fig. 5. Schematic of a tufted DCB specimen [5]

Fig. 6. Mode I delamination results